

IMPROVING FRP COMPRESSIVE PERFORMANCE THROUGH INTERMITTENT MATRIX PROPERTY MODIFICATION

Hwei Linn Khoo*^{1,2}

³ R. Trask, ² S. Pimenta, and ¹ P. Robinson

¹ Department of Aeronautics, Imperial College London, London, UK

² Department of Mechanical Engineering, Imperial College London, London, UK

³ Bristol Composites Institute, University of Bristol, Bristol, UK

* hlk18@ic.ac.uk

IMPERIAL

The Composites Centre

for research, modelling, testing and training in advanced composites

Bristol Composites Institute

FRP COMPRESSIVE FAILURE

MOTIVATION

- Matrix-dominated failure under compression (*e.g. kink-band formation*) remains a limiting factor in FRPs.
- This consequently limits FRPs' range of applicability and design.

FRP Compressive failure

Wang, Y. *et al.* (2021) doi:10.1016/j.compscitech.2021.108929.

Traditional improvement strategy:

- Uniform strengthening

Novel strategy:

- Targeted strengthening

AIM

*To what extent can intermittent **strong–weak matrix modification** benefit **CFRPs in compression**?*

WORKFLOW

1) Select
FRP architecture

2) Develop and explore
intermittent modification strategies

3) Benchmark against
homogenous matrix baselines

Strong matrix strength and stiffness is 1.5 X that of the weak matrix.

UNIDIRECTIONAL FRPS

- Optimised architecture for composite strength and stiffness
- Most influential geometric defect: fibre misalignment angle θ^f

UNIDIRECTIONAL FRPS HOMOGENEOUS MATRIX BASELINE RESPONSE

UNIDIRECTIONAL FRPS HOMOGENEOUS MATRIX BASELINE RESPONSE

UNIDIRECTIONAL FRPS HOMOGENEOUS MATRIX BASELINE RESPONSE

Strong matrix

RoM matrix
(50% strong +
50% weak)

Weak matrix

UNIDIRECTIONAL FRPS

HOMOGENEOUS MATRIX BASELINES AS BENCHMARKS

Normalised Compressive Strength

$$\tilde{X} = \frac{X - X_{\text{weak}}}{X_{\text{strong}} - X_{\text{weak}}}$$

Normalised Plastic Energy Dissipated (at failure)

$$\tilde{U} = \frac{U - U_{\text{weak}}}{U_{\text{strong}} - U_{\text{weak}}}$$

Strong matrix
performance
= 1

Weak matrix
performance
= 0

INTERMITTENT MODIFICATION STRATEGY

A. MANUFACTURE-FRIENDLY

- Intermittent matrix follows **regular checkerboard grid pattern**
- Discretised transitions
- Size of grid determined from spatial parameters of FRP θ^f field

INTERMITTENT MODIFICATION STRATEGY

A. MANUFACTURE-FRIENDLY

UD FRPS ~ MANUFACTURE-FRIENDLY INTERMITTENT MATRIX MODIFIED FRPS

At peak stress X

UD FRPS ~ MANUFACTURE-FRIENDLY INTERMITTENT MATRIX MODIFIED FRPS

UD FRPS ~ MANUFACTURE-FRIENDLY EFFECT OF PATTERN SIZE

w	h
$l_x = 0.73 \text{ mm}$	$l_y = 1.35 \text{ mm}$
l_x	$1.5 \cdot l_y$
$2 \cdot l_x$	$2 \cdot l_y$
$2 \cdot l_x$	$3 \cdot l_y$

INTERMITTENT MODIFICATION STRATEGY

B. DEFECT-ORIENTED

- Intermittent matrix variation follows variation of **FRP** $|\theta^f|$ **field.**
- Enables targeted strengthening of weakest regions
 - i.e. regions with high $|\theta^f|$

UD FRPS ~ DEFECT-ORIENTED INTERMITTENT MATRIX MODIFIED FRPS

At peak stress X_{int}

UNIDIRECTIONAL FRPS

COMPARING INTERMITTENT MATRIX MODIFICATION STRATEGIES

WOVEN FRPs

2D cross-sectional slice of a woven FRP

- Efficient at reinforcing multiple directions within single ply
- Increased drapability and conformability for complex structures
- Fail by initial kink-banding of individual tows, followed by global failure.

WOVEN FRPS

HOMOGENEOUS MATRIX BASELINE RESPONSE

At peak stress X

WOVEN FRPS

HOMOGENEOUS MATRIX BASELINE RESPONSE

WOVEN FRPS

HOMOGENEOUS MATRIX BASELINE RESPONSE

At peak stress X

andom8 L7950=true rom1.odt Abaqus/Standard 2023.HF3 Sun Jun 08 20:3

WOVEN FRPS

HOMOGENEOUS MATRIX BASELINE RESPONSE

INTERMITTENT MODIFICATION STRATEGY

C. MANUFACTURE-FRIENDLY + DEFECT-ORIENTED

- Strong matrix regions are centred on the max-crimp (high $|\theta^f|$) region.
- Discretised transitions.

Weak Strong

WOVEN FRPS

INTERMITTENT MATRIX MODIFIED FRPS

WOVEN FRPS

INTERMITTENT MATRIX MODIFIED FRPS

Normalised Strength

Low stacking randomness

High stacking randomness

Normalised Plastic Energy Dissipated (at peak FRP stress)

KEY TAKEAWAYS

- Intermittent matrix modification strategies are **most useful** if the FRP architecture allows for **high predictability of failure locations**.
- If critical defects can be easily predetermined, those areas can be feasibly targeted and strengthened, allowing for significant benefit to be gained.

UD FRP	Woven FRP
Low damage predictability	High damage predictability
Limited potential for intermittent matrix modification	High potential for intermittent matrix modification

Next COMP

Next Generation
Fibre-Reinforced Composites

<https://nextcomp.ac.uk>

I would like to acknowledge funding which supported this work from the UK Research and Innovation - EPSRC Programme Grant; Next Generation Fibre-Reinforced Composites: A Full Scale Redesign for Compression (EP/T011653/1)

A collaboration between Imperial College London and University of Bristol

IMPERIAL

